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DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15121737>*Volodymyr S. Ishchenko¹, Anatoliy I. Gozhenko²***NEURO-ENDOCRINE REGULATION OF THE CLEARANCE OF URIC ACID**¹International Humanitarian University, Odessa, Ukraine²Ukrainian Research Institute for Medicine of Transport of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine**Authors' Information:**Gozhenko A.I. – ORCID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0001-7413-4173>

Summary. Ishchenko Volodymyr S., Gozhenko Anatoliy I. **NEURO-ENDOCRINE REGULATION OF THE CLEARANCE OF URIC ACID.** - ¹International Humanitarian University, Odessa, Ukraine; ²Ukrainian Research Institute for Medicine of Transport of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine, Odessa; e-mail; ishchenkovov@gmail.com. **Background.** On the first stage of project "Neuro-endocrine regulation of the clearance of nitrogenous metabolites" implementation, we found out of peculiarities of metabolic and neuro-endocrine accompaniments of urate-losing and urate-retaining kidneys. In next study, revealed 32 variables (in addition to clearance, fractional excretion, uricosuria and uricemia by definition, 14 EEG, 7 HRV, 4 blood pressure, and 3 endocrine), according to the totality of which all 4 clusters of uric acid clearance clearly differ from each other. The aim of this study is to analyze the relationships between uric acid clearance and neurogenic, endocrine and immune variables and identify among them the factors regulating the former. **Materials and Methods.** The object of observations were patients with chronic pyelonephritis in the phase of remission (34 males aged 23-70 years and 10 females aged 33-76 years). Testing was performed twice - on admission and after 7-10 days of standard balneotherapy on Truskavets' Spa. The content of uric acid and creatinine was determined in daily urine and blood serum. In addition, the serum level of the main adaptation hormones and immune parameters was determined. The state of the autonomic and central nervous systems was assessed by the HRV and EEG methods respectively. Immune status evaluated by routine methods. **Results.** The strong canonical correlation between the uric acid clearance and the constellation of HRV&EEG parameters as well as PTH, diastolic blood pressure, microbial count of Staph. aureus and Stange's test were detected ($R=0.791$; $p<10^{-6}$). **Conclusion.** Uric acid clearance is subject to the regulatory effects of central and autonomous nervous as well as endocrine and immune systems.

Key words: uric acid clearance, EEG, HRV, adaptation hormones, immunity, chronic pyelonephritis.

Реферат. Іщенко В. С., Гоженко А. І. **НЕЙРОЕНДОКРИННА РЕГУЛЯЦІЯ КЛІРЕНСУ СЕЧОВОЇ КИСЛОТИ.** **Вступ.** На першому етапі реалізації проекту «Нейро-ендокринна регуляція кліренсу азотистих метаболітів» ми з'ясували особливості метаболічного та нейроендокринного супроводу урат-втрачаючих і урат-утримуючих нирок. У наступному дослідженні було виявлено 32 змінні (крім кліренсу, фракційної екскреції, урикозурії та урикемії за визначенням, 14 EEG, 7 HRV, 4 артеріального тиску та 3 ендокринних), за сукупністю яких усі 4 кластери кліренсу сечової кислоти чітко відрізняються один від одного. Мета: проаналізувати зв'язки між кліренсом сечової кислоти та нейрогенними, ендокринними та імунними змінними та визначення серед них факторів, що регулюють перші.

Матеріали та методи. Об'єктом спостереження були хворі на хронічний пієлонефрит у фазі ремісії (34 чоловіки віком 23–70 років та 10 жінок віком 33–76 років). Тестування проводили двічі - при надходженні та після 7-10 днів стандартного бальнеотерапії на курорті Трускавець. У добовій сечі та сироватці крові визначали вміст сечової кислоти та креатиніну. Крім того, визначали сироватковий рівень основних гормонів адаптації та показники імунітету. Стан вегетативної та центральної нервової системи оцінювали відповідно методом ВСР та ЕЕГ. Оцінка імунного статусу звичайними методами. Результати. Сильна канонічна кореляція між кліренсом сечової кислоти та констеляцією параметрів ВСР та ЕЕГ, а також ПТГ, діастолічного артеріального тиску, мікробного числа *Staph. aureus* та пробу Штанге ($R=0,791$; $p<10^{-6}$). **Висновок.** Очищення сечової кислоти залежить від регуляторного впливу центральної та автономної нервової, а також ендокринної та імунної систем.

Ключові слова: кліренс сечової кислоти, ЕЕГ, ВСР, гормони адаптації, імунітет, хронічний пієлонефрит.

Introduction

On the first stage of project "Neuro-endocrine regulation of the clearance of nitrogenous metabolites" implementation, we found out of peculiarities of metabolic and neuro-endocrine accompaniments of urate-losing and urate-retaining kidneys. Using the method of discriminant analysis, it was found that constitutionally distinct types of uric acid metabolism are characterized, in addition to clearance, uricosuria and uricemia by definition, by specific constellations of 11 metabolic and 7 autonomic variables as well as serum calcitonin and Stange's test [Ishchenko VS et al., 2024]. In next study, performed on the same sample of patients, the battery of tests was supplemented with electroencephalography and immunity. The method of discriminant analysis revealed 32 variables (in addition to clearance, fractional excretion, uricosuria and uricemia by definition, 14 EEG, 7 HRV, 4 blood pressure, and 3 endocrine), according to the totality of which all 4 clusters of uric acid clearance clearly differ from each other (classification accuracy 100%) [Ishchenko VS & Anchev AS, 2024].

The aim: to analyze the relationships between uric acid clearance and neurogenic, endocrine and immune variables and identify among them the factors regulating the former.

Materials and methods

The object of observations were patients with chronic pyelonephritis in the phase of remission (34 males aged 23-70 years and 10 females aged 33-76 years). Testing was performed twice - on admission and after 7-10 days of standard balneotherapy on Truskavets Spa (drinking of Naftussya bioactive water, applications of ozokerite, mineral pools) [Chebanenko OI et al. 1997; Lukovych YuS et al., 2015].

The battery of tests was created in line with concepts functional-metabolic continuum [Gozhenko AI, 2016] and neuro-endocrine-immune network [Korda MM et al., 2024; 2024a]. Daily urine was collected on the eve, in which was determined the concentration of uric acid (estimated by uricase method) and creatinine (by Jaffe's color reaction by Popper's method) [Goryachkovskiy AM, 1998]. The same metabolic parameters were determined in serum. In addition, we determined serum levels of main adaptation hormones such as Cortisol, Aldosterone, Testosterone, Triiodothyronine, Calcitonin and PTH. In order to identify neurogenic regulatory factors, we recorded HRV and EEG parameters as well as blood pressure in triple test [Popovych IL et al., 2022]. The good old Stange's and Genchy's tests [Biletsky SV & Gozhenko AI, 2007] were carried out on occasion.

To assess the parameters of HRV, recorded electrocardiogram during 7 min in II lead (hardware-software complex "CardioLab+HRV" produced by "KhAI-Medica", Kharkiv, Ukraine). For further analyses the following parameters HRV were selected. Temporal parameters (Time Domain Methods): heart rate (HR), the standard deviation of all NN intervals (SDNN), the square root of the mean of the sum of the squares of differences between adjacent NN intervals (RMSSD), the percent of interval differences of successive NN intervals greater than 50 ms (pNN_{50}), triangular index (TNN). Spectral parameters (Frequency Domain Methods): power

spectral density (PSD) bands of HRV: high-frequency (HF, range 0,4÷0,15 Hz), low-frequency (LF, range 0,15÷0,04 Hz), very low-frequency (VLF, range 0,04÷0,015 Hz) and ultralow-frequency (ULF, range 0,015÷0,003 Hz). We calculated classical indexes: LF/HF, LFnu=100%•LF/(LF+HF), Centralization Index (VLF+LF)/HF [Heart Rate Variability, 1996; Bernston GG et al., 1997; Baevsky R. & Chernikova A, 2017; Shaffer F & Ginsberg JP, 2017].

Simultaneously qEEG recorded at rest a hardware-software complex “NeuroCom Standard” (KhAI Medica, Kharkiv, Ukraine) monopolar in 16 loci (Fp1, Fp2, F3, F4, F7, F8, C3, C4, T3, T4, P3, P4, T5, T6, O1, O2) by 10-20 international system, with the reference electrodes A and Ref on the earlobes. Two minutes after the eyes had been closed, 25 sec of artifact free EEG data were collected by computer. Among the options considered the average EEG amplitude (μV), average frequency (Hz), frequency deviation (Hz), index (%), absolute ($\mu\text{V}^2/\text{Hz}$) and relative (%) PSD of basic rhythms: β (35÷13 Hz), α (13÷8 Hz), θ (8÷4 Hz) and δ (4÷0,5 Hz) in all loci, according to the instructions of the device.

We calculated also for HRV and each locus of EEG the Entropy (h) of normalized PSD using Popovych’s IL formulas [Popadynets OO et al., 2020; Gozhenko AI et al., 2021]:

$$h_{\text{EEG}} = - [\text{PSD}\alpha \cdot \log_2 \text{PSD}\alpha + \text{PSD}\beta \cdot \log_2 \text{PSD}\beta + \text{PSD}\theta \cdot \log_2 \text{PSD}\theta + \text{PSD}\delta \cdot \log_2 \text{PSD}\delta] / \log_2 4;$$

$$h_{\text{HRV}} = - [\text{PSDHF} \cdot \log_2 \text{PSDHF} + \text{PSDLF} \cdot \log_2 \text{PSDLF} + \text{PSDVLF} \cdot \log_2 \text{PSDVLF} + \text{PSDULF} \cdot \log_2 \text{PSDULF}] / \log_2 4.$$

Immune status evaluated as described in the manuals [Lapovets LYE & Lutsyk BD, 2004]. For phenotyping subpopulations of lymphocytes used the methods of rosette formation with sheep erythrocytes on which adsorbed monoclonal antibodies against receptors CD3, CD4, CD8, CD25, CD22 and CD56 from company "Granum" (Kharkiv) with visualization under light microscope with immersion system. The state of humoral immunity judged by the concentration in serum of Immunoglobulins of classes G, A, M (ELISA, analyser “Immunochem”, USA) and circulating immune complexes (by polyethylene glycol precipitation method).

Parameters of phagocytic function of neutrophils estimated as described by Kovbasnyuk MM [Kulchynskiy AB et al., 2016]. The objects of phagocytosis served daily cultures of *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC N 25423 F49) as typical specimen for Gram-positive Bacteria and *Escherichia coli* (O55 K59) as typical representative of Gram-negative Bacteria. Take into account the following parameters of Phagocytosis: activity (percentage of neutrophils, in which found microbes - Hamburger’s Phagocytic Index PhI), intensity (number of microbes absorbed one phagocytes - Microbial Count MC or Right’s Index) and completeness (percentage of dead microbes - Killing Index KI).

For statistical analysis used the software package “Microsoft Excell” and “Statistica 6.4 StatSoft Inc” (Tulsa, OK, USA).

Results and discussion

Screening of correlation coefficients revealed the closest relationship between uric acid clearance and PSD of LF band HRV (Fig. 1).

The LF band was previously called the baroreceptor range because it mainly reflects baroreceptor activity during resting conditions. LF power may be produced by both the vagal and sympathetic influences, and blood pressure regulation *via* baroreceptors, primarily by the vagal nerve, or by baroreflex activity alone. The sympathetic system does not appear to produce rhythms much above 0,1 Hz, while the parasympathetic system can be observed to affect heart rhythms down to 0,05 Hz. When LF is calculated while sitting upright during resting conditions (as in our situation), the primary contributors are vagal influences and baroreflex activity - not sympathetic activity. During periods of slow respiration rates, vagal activity can easily generate oscillations in the heart rhythms that cross over into the LF band [Shaffer F & Ginsberg JP, 2017].

As a result of the regression analysis with stepwise exclusion of variables until reaching the maximum value of Adjusted R^2 , 6 HRV variables were included in the model (Table 1).

Fig. 1. Scatterplot of correlation between the PSD of LF band HRV (X-line) and Clearance of Uric acid (Y-line)

Table 1.

Regression Summary for UA clearance against HRV variables

R=0,614; R²=0,376; Adjusted R²=0,330; F_(6,8)=8,2; p<10⁻⁵; SE: 3,9 mL/min

N=88		Beta	St. Err. of Beta	B	St. Err. of B	t ₍₈₁₎	p-level
Variables	r			Intercept			
LF band HRV, msec ²	0,48	1,058	0,222	0,006	0,001	4,77	10 ⁻⁵
Total Power HRV, msec ²	0,32	-1,178	0,404	-0,003	0,001	-2,91	0,005
VLF band HRV, msec ²	0,28	0,843	0,318	0,005	0,002	2,66	0,009
Triangular index HRV, un.	0,23	-0,348	0,176	-0,430	0,218	-1,98	0,051
ULF band HRV, %	-0,27	-0,155	0,091	-0,170	0,099	-1,71	0,091
VLF band HRV, %	-0,20	-0,268	0,144	-0,076	0,041	-1,86	0,067

The physiological interpretation of the VLF band remains a matter of debate.

Akselrod S et al. [1981] in pioneering experiment illustrated that after parasympathetic blockade the amplitude of the VLF peak is reduced; β -sympathetic blockade tends to reduce the VLF peak's amplitude, but this effect is not consistent because of the low tonic level of sympathetic activity in the resting dog. Increasing the activity of either the sympathetic or parasympathetic nervous system augments the area under the VLF peak. Therefore, both SNS and PSNS may mediate the VLF fluctuations. Selective blockade of renin-angiotensin system (by converting enzyme inhibitor) lead to 2-4.5-fold increase in the area under the VLF peak. Taylor JA et al. [1998] in young healthy subjects observed that β -adrenergic blockade had no significant effect on VLF power. ACE blockade modestly (approximately 21%) increased VLF power in the supine (but not upright tilt) position; atropine, given alone or with atenolol, decreased VLF band by 92%. Authors concluded that although VLF band are influenced by the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system, they depend primarily on the presence of parasympathetic outflow. Del Valle-Mandragon L et al. [2022] showing that during hemodialysis angiotensin II had a **positive** correlation with VLF band (r=0.390) and with LF/HF (r=0.359) while a negative correlation with LF (r=-0.262) and HF (r=-0.383) bands. Therefore, the contradictions regarding the nature of VLF connections with vagal and sympathetic tone as well as the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system remain unresolved. Besides it was shown that low VLF power has been correlated with low levels

of testosterone, while cortisol has not [Theorell T et al., 2007; Hasson D et al., 2009]. In the cohort observed by Ruzhylo SV et al. [2022], the **relative** PSD of VLF band correlates negatively with markers of vagal tone ($r=-0.44\div-0.54$), but positively with the AMo ($r=0.31$), as well as cortisol ($r=0.44$) in the complete absence of a connection with both aldosterone ($r=-0.05$) and testosterone ($r=-0.03$). So, in this specific situation, the **relative** PSD of VLF band acts as a marker of sympathetic tone and cortisol. Some experimental evidence suggests that the heart intrinsically generates the VLF rhythm and efferent SNS activity due to physical activity and stress responses modulates its amplitude and frequency [Shaffer F & Ginsberg JP, 2017].

The ULF band ($0,015\div0,003$ Hz) registered by complex "CardioLab+HRV" is actually the lower zone of the VLF band ($0,040\div0,0033$ Hz) in foreign devices. Therefore, what was stated regarding the last band applies to this one as well.

Instead, the triangular index and total power HRV are generally accepted vagal markers. It seems that vagal influences upregulate uric acid clearance, while sympathetic downregulate it. Taken together, these HRV parameters determine uric acid clearance by 37.6% (Table 1).

It is known that renal nerves constrict the renal vasculature causing decreases in renal blood flow and glomerular filtration rate. Whether renal hemodynamics are influenced by changes in renal nerve activity within the physiological range is a matter of debate [Ruzhylo S. et al., 2024]. Denton KM et al. [2004] have identified two morphologically distinct populations of nerves within the kidney, which are differentially distributed to the renal afferent and efferent arterioles. Type I nerves almost exclusively innervate the afferent arteriole whereas Type II nerves are distributed equally on the afferent and efferent arterioles. Authors have also demonstrated that Type II nerves are immuno-reactive for neuropeptide Y while Type I nerves are not. This led them to hypothesis that in the kidney, distinct populations of nerves innervate specific effector tissues and that these nerves may be selectively activated, setting the basis for the differential neural control of glomerular filtration rate. In physiological studies, authors demonstrated that differential changes in glomerular capillary pressure occurred in response to graded reflex activation of the renal nerves, compatible with their hypothesis. Thus, sympathetic outflow may be capable of selectively increasing or decreasing glomerular capillary pressure and hence glomerular filtration rate by differentially activating separate populations of renal nerves. This has important implications for our understanding of the neural control of body fluid balance in health and disease.

We also found out that the increased clearance of urates is accompanied by the strengthening, and the reduced clearance - by the weakening of both sympathetic and vagal regulatory influences [Ishchenko VS et al., 2024].

It is known also that sympathetic outflow to the kidney is regulated by major cortical, brainstem and medullary areas [DiBona GF, 2003; Johns EJ, 2014]. We specified the loci of the scalp on which the nerve structures related to the regulation of urate clearance are projected (Table 2). The influence of the central nervous system on uric acid clearance was significantly weaker than that of the autonomic system.

Table 2

Regression Summary for UA clearance against EEG variables

$R=0,448$; $R^2=0,201$; Adjusted $R^2=0,141$; $F_{(6,8)}=3,4$; $p=0,005$; SE: 4,5 mL/min

N=88		Beta	St. Err. of Beta	B	St. Err. of B	$t_{(81)}$	p-level
Variables	r		Intcpt	1,38	4,12	0,33	0,739
Deviation θ, Hz	0,27	0,259	0,103	2,976	1,177	2,53	0,013
PSD F7-α, %	0,24	0,323	0,133	0,111	0,046	2,44	0,017
PSD F8 Entropy	0,16	0,124	0,107	3,008	2,594	1,16	0,250
PSD P4-β, %	0,16	0,222	0,123	0,094	0,052	1,80	0,075
Amplitude-β, μV	0,15	-0,164	0,100	-0,250	0,153	-1,64	0,104
PSD Fp2-δ, %	-0,16	0,158	0,145	0,038	0,034	1,09	0,278

Taken together, autonomic and central neurogenic influences determine uric acid clearance by 47.8% (Table 3 and Fig. 2).

Table 3

Regression Summary for UA clearance against HRV&EEG variablesR=0,691; R²=0,478; Adjusted R²=0,418; F_(9,8)=7,9; p<10⁻⁵; SE: 3,7 mL/min

N=88		Beta	St. Err. of Beta	B	St. Err. of B	t ₍₇₈₎	p-level
Variables	r		Intercept	8,10	3,08	2,63	0,010
LF band HRV, msec ²	0,48	1,034	0,208	0,0058	0,0012	4,98	10 ⁻⁵
Total Power HRV, msec ²	0,32	-1,215	0,389	-0,0029	0,0009	-3,12	0,003
VLF band HRV, msec ²	0,28	0,891	0,309	0,0053	0,0018	2,88	0,005
Deviation θ , Hz	0,27	0,183	0,087	2,1041	1,0002	2,10	0,039
PSD F7- α , %	0,24	0,215	0,084	0,0743	0,0288	2,58	0,012
Triangular index HRV, un.	0,23	-0,319	0,167	-0,3936	0,2058	-1,91	0,059
PSD P4- β , %	0,16	0,161	0,088	0,0683	0,0374	1,83	0,072
ULF band HRV, %	-0,27	-0,088	0,088	-0,0965	0,0959	-1,01	0,317
VLF band HRV, %	-0,20	-0,252	0,138	-0,0713	0,0390	-1,83	0,071

R=0,691; R²=0,478; $\chi^2_{(9)}$ =53; p<10⁻⁶; Λ Prime=0,522

Fig. 2. Scatterplot of canonical correlation between the neural variables (X-line) and Clearance of Uric acid (Y-line)

The Stange's test correlates with the relative PSD of β -rhythm in Fp1 ($r = -0.30$) and O1 ($r = -0.21$) loci, that is, can be considered a neural marker.

Now we found the connection of urate clearance with diastolic pressure as well as its reactivity, which are subject to neurogenic regulatory influences [Popovych IL et al., 2022; Kozyavkina NV et al., 2024]. Together with parathyroid hormone and the intensity of the phagocytic function of blood neutrophils, this neuro-endocrine-immune constellation of regulatory factors determines uric acid clearance by 62.5% (Table 4 and Fig. 3).

Table 4.

Regression Summary for UA clearance against regulating factorsR=0,791; R²=0,625; Adjusted R²=0,560; F_(13,7)=9,5; p<10⁻⁶; SE: 3,2 mL/min

N=88		Beta	St. Err. of Beta	B	St. Err. of B	t ₍₇₄₎	p-level
Variables	r		Intercept	-8,22	8,21	-1,00	0,320
LF band HRV, msec ²	0,48	0,814	0,191	0,0046	0,0011	4,25	10 ⁻⁴
Total Power HRV, msec ²	0,32	-0,638	0,404	-0,0015	0,0010	-1,58	0,118
Parathyroid hormone, pM/L	0,30	0,202	0,079	0,8636	0,3373	2,56	0,013
BP diastolic, mmHg	0,30	0,185	0,083	0,0889	0,0401	2,22	0,030
VLF band HRV, msec ²	0,28	0,445	0,267	0,0026	0,0016	1,66	0,101
Deviation θ , Hz	0,27	0,134	0,078	1,5370	0,8953	1,72	0,090
PSD F7- α , %	0,24	0,156	0,073	0,0536	0,0253	2,12	0,037
Pd3/Pd1 Ratio	0,23	0,153	0,074	13,393	6,5258	2,05	0,044
RMSSD HRV, msec	0,16	-0,213	0,150	-0,0595	0,0420	-1,42	0,160
ULF band HRV, %	-0,27	-0,136	0,078	-0,1481	0,0854	-1,73	0,087
Micr. Count of St. aur., B/Ph	-0,26	-0,177	0,074	-0,1051	0,0440	-2,39	0,019
VLF band HRV, %	-0,20	-0,134	0,121	-0,0380	0,0343	-1,11	0,271
Stange's test, sec	-0,15	-0,121	0,074	-0,0363	0,0222	-1,64	0,106

R=0,791; R²=0,625; $\chi^2_{(13)}=78$; p<10⁻⁶; Λ Prime=0,375**Fig. 3.** Scatterplot of canonical correlation between the neuro-endocrine-immune variables (X-line) and Clearance of Uric acid (Y-line)

Possible mechanisms of influence on uric acid clearance of the last two factors will be the subject of a separate analysis.

Conclusion

Uric acid clearance is subject to the regulatory effects of central and autonomous nervous as well as endocrine and immune systems. The closest relationship revealed between PSD of LF

band HRV as marker of vagal tone and baroreflex activity. In addition, other vagal markers have a upregulating effect, while markers of sympathetic tone have a downregulating effect. Taken together, autonomic influences determine uric acid clearance by 37.6%. The influence of the central nervous system on uric acid clearance was significantly weaker than that of the autonomic system (20.1%). Taken together, autonomic and central neurogenic influences determine uric acid clearance by 47.8%. Other enhancing factors are parathyroid hormone and diastolic blood pressure, whereas the Stange's test and the intensity of the phagocytic function of blood neutrophils are downregulating factors. This neuro-endocrine-immune constellation of regulatory factors determines uric acid clearance by 62.5%.

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HEPATOPROTECTIVE THERAPY EFFICACY IN OBSTRUCTIVE HEPATOBILIARY DISEASES: A PROSPECTIVE RANDOMIZED STUDY

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Summary. Maksymenko M., Kulivets O., Havryliuk R. **HEPATOPROTECTIVE THERAPY EFFICACY IN OBSTRUCTIVE HEPATOBILIARY DISEASES: A PROSPECTIVE RANDOMIZED STUDY.** - O.O. Bogomolets National Medical University, Kyiv, Ukraine; e-mail: mihvasmaks@gmail.com; romangavryliuk2@gmail.com. **Introduction.** Obstructive diseases of the hepatobiliary system present a complex set of clinical challenges characterized by impaired bile outflow and progressive hepatocellular damage. Despite significant advances in interventional and surgical approaches, liver dysfunction associated with these disorders continues to substantially impact patient morbidity and mortality. Hepatoprotective agents have emerged as a potential adjunctive therapeutic strategy, although their efficacy in managing hepatobiliary obstruction remains insufficiently investigated. **The purpose:** to assess the efficacy and clinical feasibility of hepatoprotective therapy in obstructive hepatobiliary diseases. **Materials and methods.** A prospective randomized cohort study was conducted from 2020 to 2024 at the Surgical Department №2 of the Kyiv Municipal Clinical Hospital of Emergency Medical Care, analyzing the treatment results of 139 patients with obstructive biliary disease (54 men, 85 women). Patients were randomly stratified into two groups: a control group receiving standard conservative therapy and a hepatoprotective therapy group receiving supplementary treatment with Remaxol, Silymarin, and S-adenosylmethionine for 21 consecutive days. **Results.** Biochemical parameter analysis revealed significant improvements in patients receiving combined hepatoprotective therapy compared to the control group. On day 7, patients administered hepatoprotectors demonstrated a 46.7% decrease in total bilirubin (reducing to 111.2 ± 22.1 $\mu\text{mol/L}$), compared to a 39.5% decrease (to 128.0 ± 23.5 $\mu\text{mol/L}$) in the control group ($p < 0.05$). Liver enzyme levels exhibited a more pronounced improvement in the hepatoprotector therapy group, with alanine aminotransferase (ALT) decreasing from 175 ± 25 U/L to 52 ± 5 U/L (a 70.3% reduction) on day 7, contrasted with a 45.6% decrease in the control group (from 182 ± 22 U/L to 99 ± 10 U/L) ($p < 0.001$). Cholestatic markers also demonstrated superior responsiveness to hepatoprotective therapy. Alkaline phosphatase (ALP) decreased by 53.4%, and gamma-glutamyl